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Philosophy:

The Journal of Engineering Management Science is innovative and research-based in any area of Engineering & Management.

The Journal of Engineering & Management welcomes to submit data- case studies for publication. All authors should contribute to advancing existing knowledge and/or practices in the field and hence should endeavor to be original and critical.

Authors should indicate an understanding of the relevant literature and the contribution of their submissions to this body of knowledge. Empirical articles should have an appropriate methodology and be able to relate their findings to the existing literature.

Theoretical articles must attempt to show how they extend existing theory.

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Contributors: Every research-oriented individual, institution, and every research student, faculty member anywhere in the world is invited to explore fruitful research with Excel Journal.

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A critical reflection on digital initiation by G.O.I. (Government of India) for H.E. (Higher Education)

** Muntajeeb Ali Baig*

Introduction

As cited by K. Srinivas, "The key to successful use of technology, in 21st-century classroom teaching, learning and assessment lie not in hardware and software but in the empowerment of teachers" (personal communication, November 28, 2018). In his lecture on "Digital initiatives of (G.O.I.) The government of India for (H.E.) Higher Education", K. Srinivas, explains about digital initiatives taken by the government of India for higher education, further he mentioned about Massive Online Open Courses (MOOCs), such as SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active Learning for Young Aspiring Minds), which provides online courses from primary to higher education. This programme is designed to achieve the three cardinal principles of education policy viz. access, equity, and quality (SWAYAM, 2016). SWAYAM platform is indigenously developed by Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) and All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) with the help of Microsoft. SWAYAM (<https://swayam.gov.in>) is providing a large number of courses from covering school, undergraduate, post-graduate, engineering, law, and other professional courses.

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in 2008; a cMOOC is taught according to connectivist principles, combining open learning with distributed content (Series, 1865).

1) **MOOC:** The traditional MOOCs, are a form of xMOOCs, these are MOOCs that follow a more traditional structure and delivery approach, are probably offered by a recognized academic institution, and are where the course is highly structured and with clear expectations for how the student will engage with the course (Series, 1865).

2) **C-MOOC:** As cited in (Editor & Rud, n.d.), George Siemens drew a very sharp line between c-MOOCs and x-MOOCs. According to George Siemens, the cMOOC model emphasizes creation, creativity, autonomy, and social networking learning, whereas the x-MOOC model emphasizes 'a more traditional learning approach through video presentations and short quizzes and testing. Put another way, cMOOCs focus on knowledge creation and generation whereas an x-MOOCs focus on knowledge duplication' (Editor & Rud, n.d.).

Literature Review

In their findings (Li, Zhang, Bonk, & Guo, 2015), conclude that the course designed should be based on comprehensive learner analysis and learner-centered. In a flipped classroom learners have more autonomy with their own pace of learning, in the flipped classroom, the instructor should have more attention to interaction design, including the type and forms of face to face and online interaction. In their report on "ELI Focus session", (Diaz, Brown, & Pelletier, 2013), says that, MOOCs may serve as a rich source of content as a sort of open textbook offering a variety of media: text, video, simulations, and discussions, all excellent supports for active learning. In some of findings issues emerged regarding the MOOC, (Brown, Busby, Kline, & Clark, 2013) observe that, initially MOOCs, were offered with no fees, credits were not allowed and had no prerequisite or admission requirements, students were enrolled according to their interest and enrichment or professional development, but it was observed that most of the students who enrolled did not complete their courses, within the "no credit context", as cited in (Brown et al., 2013), the course completions are estimated to be less than 10%, though it is a significant number since enrollment is in lakhs (Brown et al., 2013).

Conclusion
MOOCs promise to open up higher education by providing accessible, flexible, affordable and fast-track completion of universities courses for free or at a low cost for learners who are interested in learning. The popularity of MOOCs has attracted a great deal of attention from Higher Education (H.E.), institutions and private investors around the world seeking to build their brands and to enter the education market. Institutions will need to look more closely at and learn from the different initiatives outside traditional institutions that are developing new business, financial and revenue models to meet the different needs of new groups of learners in an open HE marketplace. Open education brings new opportunities for innovation in higher education that will allow institutions and academics to explore new online learning models and innovative practices in teaching and learning. At a national and international level, new frameworks for HE funding structures, quality insurance, and accreditation to support different approaches and models for delivering higher education will be required. Policy makers will need to embrace openness and make education more affordable and accessible for all and at the same time be profitable for the institutions in an open higher education ecosystem.

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the government of India also started SWAYAM PRABHA, which is a group of 32 direct to Home (DTH) channels, these channels are telecasting high-quality educational programs on myriads of disciplines, 24X7 basis using the GSAT-15 satellite (K. Srinivas, personal communication, November 28, 2018). SWAYAM PRABHA, telecast four hours content every day, these programs are repeated 5 more times in a day, allowing the students to choose the time of their convenience. The contents are provided by NPTEL, UGC, CEC, IGNOU, NCERT and NIOS. The INFLIBNET Centre maintains the web portal (Inflibnet, n.d.). Beside this Digital Object Repositories were also provided through the National Academic Depositories, this depository has audio, video, text, images, books and documents which can be accessed and used by the learners free of cost under G.N.U., Licensed. A large number of e-books has been provided by N.D.C., which can be accessed at anytime and anyplace (K. Srinivas, personal communication, November 28, 2018). K. Srinivas stressed presenting content courses on four quadrants shown in figure 1, (personal communication, November 28, 2018).

Figure 1 QUADRANTS

(K. Srinivas, personal communication, November 28, 2018), has given 5 stages for designing, disseminating and developing effective and efficient MOOC courses, these are as follows;

- a) **Content Writing:** In the knowledge society quality content is very important, main challenge in creating MOOC courses is creating creative e-content in form of animation, simulations, virtual labs, videos, audios, and e-books according to the needs of the learners.
- b) **Content Delivering:** Higher education in India is expanding through Formal Non Formal education, thus there is a need to disseminate mass content masses, through MOOC courses and SWAYAM Prabha(SWAYAM, 2017).
- c) **Content Transactions:** Transaction of MOOC courses are done through a Learning Management System, such as MOODLE, A-Tutor, Eliademy, Forma LM Dokeos, Opigno, and OpenOLAT.
- d) **Motivating Learners:** Motivation of a learner is important in the completion of the courses, thus the design of a course, quality of e-content, and effectiveness of tools and plugins are very important in developing MOOC courses.
- e) **Engaging learners for the completing of the courses:** In Online courses drop-out rates are higher, thus engaging learners in a course is very important. In the research (Shannon A Riggs, 2009), observed that a well-designed and student centered course based on active learning is as effective as face-to-face instructions.

As cited in the study, (Devgun, 2013) concludes that Indian students can have an edge in the global market by enrolling in the courses provided by the MOOC. Further, (Devgun 2013) elaborates that Indian students can leverage MOOC to stay competitive. In their findings, (Jain, 2014), concluded that in implementing MOOC in higher education the stakeholders face many challenges, and it requires significant policy measures to make them mainstream, especially in the formal sector where credits are the currency. As cited in, (Brown et al., 2013), learners are motivated in the online learning through rewards in the forms of badges called as a 'Digital badges', these validate learner learning whether it occurs inside or outside the academy (Brown et al., 2013). In their research (Kop, 2011), showed that MOOCs provide 'connectivist environment' where learners get encouragement through the "social presence" of the teacher and learner and they feel the sense the belongingness and built confidence through the active participants. In their study, (Abeer & Miri, 2014), concluded that five learning competencies that may affect students participation, persistence and continuity in learning a MOOC: linguistic competence in English, prior knowledge in the subject matter, broad-mindedness, self-regulation and self-efficacy, and communication skills.